

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LAFAYETTE****FIRST NAME: LEV****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 3****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied ~~X~~ UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author ~~X~~ did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author ~~X~~ did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: LibreOffice 24.8.1.2 on Ubuntu Linux 20.4.6 LTS. Reviewed with MS-Word 365.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is a style guide?**

- The set of rules established by Euclid University for the formatting of documents for postgraduate study that must be adhered to to prevent plagiarism.
- The documentation of an approach to elements of a writing style associated with disciplines and professions to ensure that the finished publication is coherent and consistent.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 41.

- A collection of recommendations that allow an author to write in a more stylish and poetic manner, independent and distinct from the substance of an essay.
- The various review suggestions made to a document by a Grammarly professional account for corrections, clarity, and engagement.

2. **What are some style differences between U.S. and British versions of the English language?**

- All the differences between U.S. and British English are documented in the ISO-8601 standard and include heteronymic, homophonic, and homonymic variations.
- Differences in spelling (e.g., plow vs. plough), differences in expression (e.g., petrol vs gasoline), differences in pronunciation (e.g., oregano, herbs).²**
- The United States has a greater population than the United Kingdom, a larger share of the global economy, publishing media, technology influence, and popular culture.

² Ibid, 25-32.

- There are no differences in style, as this represents the ability to write in a narrative in a fluid and pleasing manner.

3. **How do you guard against plagiarism?**

- Include all references from a reading list for an essay either as a bibliography or a reference list.
- Provide a citation for quotes, paraphrases, summaries, ideas and methods, and quote exact words from a source.³**
- Ensure you inform the course instructor of any additional reading material that you have studied for an essay.
- Run your essays through a plagiarism checker and include the percentage that from other sources in the essay submission.

4. **What is successful dissertation research?**

- Successful dissertation research occurs when the dissertation reaches the required word count and is submitted to EUCLID File Server.

³ Kate L. Turabian, et al. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 81.

- Successful dissertation research occurs when the dissertation allows the doctoral student to contribute to the literature while completing the research requirements.⁴**
- Successful dissertation research occurs when the researcher receives their doctoral degree, is published, and is able to take up a career in an area related to their studies.
- There is no such thing as successful dissertation research. Research is an ongoing and iterative activity with no conclusion.

5. **What source material should a researcher use as a priority?**

- A researcher should use tertiary sources first as these have gone through a process of refinement and editing by others and therefore have already been tested for reliability and acceptance by academic publishers.
- A researcher must use the sources recommended by Euclid University and only expand beyond the reading list following communication and approval from their instructor.

⁴ James P. Sampson. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 10.

- A researcher should use whatever content they can find that contributes to their research topic and working hypothesis. It is necessary to draw the widest possible net to capture all relevant opinions.
- A researcher should use primary and secondary sources first that are scholarly and credible, recommended from libraries and online databases, and tested for reliability, peer review, and contemporary analysis.⁵**

6. **What is the purpose of a literature review?**

- A literature review should be provide a list of studies that illustrate that the researcher's hypothesis is correct and is beyond reasonable dispute.
- A literature review shows the researcher's competence and awareness of existing content and elucidates gaps in prior research that require investigation addressed by the research question.⁶**
- Because previous literature is out-of-date, a literature review should identify how previous studies are no longer valid and how the researcher's new contribution will be the most relevant as an ongoing process.

⁵ Kate Turabian, op. cit., 26-35.

⁶ James P. Sampson, op. cit., 31-32.

- A literature review should show to instructors and examiners that the researcher is very aware of the subject by providing an exhaustive list of studies on the research question.

7. **What is some content should the "discussions" or "conclusion" chapter of a dissertation include?**

- Restate the research question, summarise the content and conclusion, and, most importantly, identify potential further research and identify new directions, arguments, and issues that were not discussed.
- Restate the research question, refer back to the ideas and debate examined in the literature review, and state which researcher was correct in the debate.
- Illustrate that the dissertation is a very worthy contribution to the discipline pointing out that it has resolved the research question and note the importance of the study by the practical implications that will occur.
- Restate the research question, identified gaps, possible implications in policy and theory development, limitations and potential research bias, a summary of the study.⁷**

⁷ James P. Sampson, op cit., 56-63.

8. Using the Chicago Author-Date citation style in a basic pattern, how is a single-authored book referenced at the conclusion of an essay?

- Author's Last name, First name., (Date), "Title", Publisher, Location.
- Author's First name, Last name. Date. Title. Editor(s)/Translator(s).
Publisher.
- Author's Last name, First name. Date. *Title*. Location: Publisher Press.⁸
- Author's Last name, First name initial, (Date), Title, Publisher.

9. Using the Chicago Notes-Bibliography citation style in a basic pattern and where endnotes are used for references, how are footnotes cited for substantive comments?

- Footnotes are not used for substantive comments. Substantive comments must be part of the text of the essay and references are included as endnotes.

⁸ Kate Turabian, op. cit., 143.

- Footnotes that are substantive comments are referenced numerically, just like endnotes, but must be expressed in order that they occur in the text.
- The presence of footnotes for substantive comments depends on the discipline; some (e.g., arts, law) prefer comments to be referenced as footnotes, whereas others (e.g., natural and social sciences) prefer their inclusion as endnotes.
- If a department uses endnotes for source citations substantive comments for footnotes they are labelled each page with an asterisk, followed by other superscript elements if required.⁹**

10. **Using the Chicago Author-Date citation style in a basic pattern, how is a website referenced?**

- Websites are not referenced in a scholarly document. If there is any content that contributes to an essay, it should be paraphrased.
- Author, publication or revision date, title of the page, title or description of the site, owner or sponsor of the site, the Uniform Resource Location. ¹⁰**

⁹ Kate Turabian, op. cit., 160-161.

¹⁰ Kate Turabian, op. cit., 261-262.

- Author, title of the page, title of the site, owner or sponsor of the site, publication of revision date, the Uniform Resource Location.
- Just the title of the page, and the URL is sufficient.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.